

Early detection of cyberbullying on social media networks

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Abstract

Cyberbullying is an important issue for our society and has a major negative effect on the victims, that could be even more damaging due to the frequency and high propagation allowed by technology. Therefore, the early detection of cyberbullying in social networks becomes crucial to mitigate the impact on the victims. In this article we aim to explore different approaches that take into account the time in the detection of cyberbullying in social networks. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first attempt to investigate the early detection of cyberbullying. We propose two groups of features and two early detection methods, specifically designed for this problem. We conduct an extensive evaluation using a real world dataset, following a time-aware evaluation that penalizes late detections. Our results show how we can improve state-of-the-art detection models up to 42%.

Keywords: cyberbullying, social networks, early detection, machine learning

1. Introduction

Bullying can be defined as an aggressive, intentional act or behaviour that is carried out by a group or an individual repeatedly and over time against a victim

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who can not easily defend him or herself [1]. When the aggression occurs using
5 Information Technologies (IT), such as the Internet, we talk of cyberbullying
[2].

Cyberbullying has been identified as a major issue [3] and has been docu-
mented as a national health problem [4] due to the continuous growth of online
communication and social media [5]. The percentages of individuals who have
10 experienced cyberbullying at some point during their lifetime has doubled, with
18% in 2007 and 36% in 2019 according to [6], and this is only expected to con-
tinue raising taking into account the high use of IT, social networks and mobile
devices by children and teenagers [7].

The negative effects of cyberbullying share many similarities with traditional
15 bullying [8] but, at the same time, it could be more damaging due to the fre-
quency and high propagation allowed by technology [9]. Studies have linked
cyberbullying with negative effects on psychological and physical health, aca-
demic performance [10, 11], depression [12] and a higher risk of suicidal ideation
[13, 14].

20 Consequently, an early detection of cyberbullying in social networks is para-
mount to mitigate and reduce its negative effects on the victims. Moreover, the
repetitive nature of cyberbullying makes it extremely important to detect and
terminate, as soon as possible, the cyberaggression to, on one side, identify the
aggressors and, on the other side, support the victims.

25 In this work we aim to explore different approaches that take into account
the time in the detection of cyberbullying in social networks. In the literature
there are multiple and diverse works that explore different approaches to detect
cyberbullying in social networks but, to the best of our knowledge, this is the
first attempt to investigate techniques specifically designed for an early detection
30 of cyberbullying. We focus on two different specific early detection methods,
named threshold and dual. The former follows a more simple approach, while
the latter requires two machine learning models. We also propose two new
groups of features, specifically designed for this problem. The first group is in-
tended to capture Bag-of-Words (BoW) similarities among comments, while the

35 second group will capture repetitive time aspects on the comments. We conduct an extensive evaluation using a real world dataset and follow a time-aware approach that penalizes late detections. Our results show how the threshold model is able to improve state-of-the-art detection models by 26% and dual model up to 42%.

40 The main contributions of this work could be summarised as:

- We define and characterize the cyberbullying early detection problem.
- We present two specific machine learning models (i.e. threshold and dual) for the cyberbullying early detection problem and we show the impact of two sets of features (i.e. BoW and time features) that contribute to
45 improve the performance in the cyberbullying early detection problem.
- We carry out extensive experiments using a real world dataset and following a time-aware evaluation that proves the performance improvement over state-of-the-art baselines.

The remaining of this article is organised as follows. In Section 2 we present
50 state-of-the-art on early phenomena and cyberbullying detection, with a special focus on social networks. Section 3 describes all the details of the cyberbullying early detection problem and Section 4 presents experimental evaluation and performance improvements over the baselines. Finally, Section 5 includes our conclusions and future work on this line of research.

55 **2. Related works**

2.1. Early phenomena detection on social networks

From a generic perspective, this work is related to the early detection of different phenomena or anomalies on social networks.

For example, last years, there has been a rising interest in the detection
60 of fake news [15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20], rumours [21, 22, 23, 24], missinformation [25, 26, 27] or fake profile detection [28, 29, 30] using the information published on social networks.

However, the works that explore the early detection perspective are limited. For example, [31] explores the prediction of fake news before it has been propagated on social media. With this purpose, they propose a theory-driven model that represents the news content at four language levels (lexicon-level, syntax-level, semantic-level and discourse-level) achieving 88% accuracy and outperforming all baselines considered.

Qin et al. aim at improving early detection of rumours on social networks by using novelty based features that consider the increase presence of unconfirmed information in a message with respect to trusted sources of information [32]. Their experiments using data collected from Sina Weibo, a Chinese social media service, show that their proposed method performs significantly better in terms of effectiveness than other real-time and early detection baselines. Also, [33] presents a rumour detection approach by clustering tweets by their likelihood of actually containing a disputed factual claim. The authors include in the evaluation the earliness of detection by measuring how soon a method is able to detect a rumour assuming a batch processing of one hour.

Also recently, the workshop on early risk prediction on the Internet (eRisk) at the Conference and Labs for the Evaluation Forum (CLEF) has provided different challenges oriented to the problems of detecting depression, anorexia and self-harm on the Reddit social network [34]. One of the best performing methods for the early detection of depression employed linguistic meta-information extracted from the subjects writings and developed a classifier using recurrent neural networks [35, 36]. Alternatively, the model proposed in [37, 38] uses a word-based approach that estimates risk based on different word statistics (within-class frequency, within-class significance and inter-class term significance), which obtained good results in the detection of depression and self-harm. We have also explored the early detection of depression on social media by developing specific learning models (e.g. singleton and dual), significantly improving previous works performance [39, 40].

2.2. Cyberbullying detection

Cyberbullying detection has been explored quite extensively, starting with user studies from social sciences and psychology fields, and more recently, moving to computer science, aiming at developing models for its automatic detection. 95

Al-Garadi et al. in [5] presented an extensive analysis of cyberbullying prediction models on social media and point at some open challenges such as the prediction of cyberbullying severity, human data characteristics or language dynamics. There are multiple studies that explore different machine learning alternatives in the detection of cyberbullying. In [41], the authors explore the use of Support Vector Machines (SVM) and a lexical syntactical feature to predict offensive language achieving high precision values. Dadvar et al. [42] use labelled text instances to train a SVM model for creating a gender specific cyberbullying detection system that improves the discrimination capacity. In [43], 100 the authors also use SVM to predict cyberbullying in Ask.fm social network. They present a new scheme annotation to describe the severity of cyberbullying and conclude that the detection of fine-grained categories (e.g. threats) is more challenging due to data sparsity.

In [44] the authors work on the detection of cyberbullying on a multimodal 110 social media environment, identifying several features, non only textual, but also audio and visual. Their results suggest that audio-visual features can help improve the performance of purely textual cyberbullying detectors.

Van et al. also investigate the automatic detection of cyberbullying-related posts on social media [45], both on English and Dutch. Using six natural language processing features groups (word n-grams, subjectivity lexicons, character n-grams, term lists and topic models), the proposed model outperform the baseline considered and identify false positives on implicit cyberbullying or offenses through irony. 115

The authors of [46, 47] study the detection of cyberbullying in the Vine social 120 network using several machine learning models, achieving the best results with AdaBoost, closely followed by Random Forest. Hosseinmardi et al. [48] work on the detection of cyberbullying incidents on the Instagram social network.

They use Naïve Bayes and SVM classifiers, with the latter obtaining the best performance by incorporating multi-modal text and images features as well as
125 media session data.

Some other works focus on the features considered to detect cyberbullying, for example, by analysing the social network structure among users [49, 50], combining text and images analysis techniques [51], profanity features [52, 47, 53, 54], sentiment analysis [55, 43, 56, 57] or location features [58], among others.

130 An extensive review of published research on automatic detection of cyberbullying can be found in [59] and [60]. From a global point of view, most works employ textual features, followed by sentiment attributes. User features (e.g. age, gender) and social features (e.g. number of friends or followers) are also commonly considered.

135 Interestingly, few works incorporate temporal features into their models, such as [61, 62], in order to capture the temporal and repetitive aspects of cyberbullying. Cheng et al. [61] incorporate a time interval prediction into their prediction model outperforming state-of-the-art models in terms of F1 and Area Under the Curve (AUC). In [62], the authors model the temporal dynamics of
140 cyberbullying in online sessions and show how the inclusion of these temporal features increases the performance of cyberbullying detection.

However, all previous works measure their performance regarding how successfully the model can distinguish between cyberbullying and non-cyberbullying cases using standard evaluation metrics, such as, accuracy, precision, recall, F-
145 measure or area under the curve [5, 59, 60], without taking into account the time required to produce the prediction. In this sense, to the best of our knowledge, our work is the first attempt to measure the cyberbullying detection performance taking into account, not only the accuracy of the system, but also the time required for the prediction.

150 **3. Cyberbullying early detection**

The problem of cyberbullying early detection on social networks can be considered different to cyberbullying prediction. In this case, there is a set of social media sessions, that we denote as S , where some may correspond to cyberbully aggressions. We define the social media sessions set as:

$$S = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{|S|}\}$$

Where $|S|$ denotes the number of sessions and s_i refers to session i .

Each social media session, $s \in S$, is formed by a sequence of posts, denoted as P_s , and a binary indicator, b_s , that specifies whether this specific session is considered cyberbullying ($b_s = true$) or not ($b_s = false$). The sequence of posts for a specific session will change through time and is given by:

$$P_s = (\langle P_1^s, t_1^s \rangle, \langle P_2^s, t_2^s \rangle, \dots, \langle P_n^s, t_n^s \rangle)$$

Where the tuple $\langle P_k^s, t_k^s \rangle$, $k \in [1, n]$ represents the k -th post for social media session s and t_k^s is the timestamp when post P_k^s was published.

At the same time, each post P_k^s is specified by a vector of features:

$$P_k^s = [f_{k_1}^s, f_{k_2}^s, \dots, f_{k_m}^s], k \in [1, n]$$

Given a social media session s , the objective is to detect if the session corresponds to cyberbullying but processing as few posts from P_s as possible. Therefore, our target is to learn a function $f(b_s | s, P_1^s, \dots, P_k^s)$ to predict whether a session is cyberbullying or not.

In this sense, the function will receive as input, posts from 1 to k , and it will return three possible values: $\{0, 1, 2\}$. Where 0 corresponds to a session s that is considered normal (i.e. non-cyberbullying), 1 if it is considered cyberbullying and 2 if no definitive decision can be emitted for session s after processing k posts and more posts must be read (i.e. *delay*).

3.1. Dataset

To study the cyberbullying early detection problem we will use a public dataset collected from Vine social network [46, 47]. The dataset was collected

Table 1: Dataset statistics.

	Cyberbullying	Normal	Total
Media sessions	190	771	961
Comments	16,332	61,129	77,461
Comments / session	85.96	79.29	80.61
Likes	261,009	1,667,943	1,928,952
Likes / session	1373.73	2163.35	2007.23
Average followers / user	132,299	188,413	176,611
Average following / user	4759	1971	2557
Average time span (secs)	210	240	234

using a snowball sampling method, where an initial user u is selected as a seed and then the collection continues with the users following u .

For each user, a standard information was collected (i.e. user name, full name, profile description, number of followers, number of videos posted, number of followings) and all videos posted along with their comments, number of likes and number of re-posts. A social media session is composed of a posted video along with all the likes and comments associated. Sessions with less than 15 comments have been removed from the dataset by the authors in order to have a sufficient number of comments [47]. A total of 961 sessions were labelled as cyberbullying or normal using crowdsourcing and, following [47], we required at least 60% confidence from the labelers to be considered cyberbullying.

Table 1 shows the main statistics for the dataset. In our case, each comment is considered a post for a social media session and, instead of aggregating all comments for a session [47, 46], we will work with each comment individually and determine, processing as few comments as possible, if the session can be considered cyberbullying or normal.

3.2. Features

For our experiments we start with the features that provided the best results in [47]. These features are grouped by:

- 185 • Profile owner features: that capture the characteristics of the user who posted the initial video. These features include numbers of followers and following, polarity and subjectivity of the user’s profile description.
- Media session features: number of likes, comments and sharings and polarity and subjectivity of media caption.
- 190 • Comment features: that are intended to determine the negativity associated with the comment. These features include percentage of negative comments, profane words in the comment, average polarity and subjectivity for the comments, differentiating between owner and other comments.
- Video features: intended to capture the nature of the video, these features
195 validate the emotions and content in the video.
- LDA features: top ten topics extracted using Latent Dirichlet Allocation from all comments.

We also further extend the features with two new group of characteristics that we consider may be relevant for the cyberbullying early detection problem:
200 Bag-of-Words (BoW) similarity and time aspects.

Following previous works, such as [41, 4, 43], we consider BoW similarity. In our case, we aim at computing these features without supervision. For this purpose, the training dataset is divided into two disjunctive sets: cyberbullying and non-cyberbullying sessions. The main goal of these features is to estimate the
205 likeliness between a given comment versus cyberbullying and normal comments, without considering a set of predefined terms (e.g. profane words).

For each comment, we calculate the average, standard deviation, minimum, maximum and median of the TF-IDF (Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency) similarity obtained comparing this comment to every other cyberbul-
210 lying comment. Then, the same process is repeated for the similarities with non-cyberbullying comments. In both cases, the active comments is removed from the corresponding sample.

Since cyberbullying implies a certain repetition over time, we consider relevant to include some features to capture different time aspects of the comments. This is pointed from the dataset statistics on Table 1, where we can observe a shorter time span for cyberbullying sessions. Figure 1 represents the time between two consecutive comments, both for cyberbullying and non-cyberbullying comments. From the figure we observe how there is a higher number of comments produced in a very short time span (a few seconds) for cyberbullying, and then, in the long tail, both types behave uniformly.

For this purpose, we include features that measure the time difference between two consecutive comments. We differentiate two cases: the time difference with last comment and the time difference considering all previous comments. In both cases, we aggregate them by calculating the average, median, maximum and minimum values.

Figure 1: Time difference between two consecutive comments for cyberbullying and non-cyberbullying.

3.3. Baselines

As baselines we will consider the models reported on [47] that achieved best performance results: Random Forest (*RF*), AdaBoost (*AB*), Extra Tree (*ET*), linear Support Vector Classification (*SVC*) and Logistic Regression (*LR*).

230 Since standard classification models provide a binary output, in order to predict if a session is considered cyberbullying or not (i.e. no delay result can be generated), we use a simple adaptation of the baselines considering a fixed number of input comments. Therefore, for each baseline model we consider four pre-established input comments: 1, 5, 10 and 15.

235 For example, the Random Forest model will be presented with 1, 5, 10 and 15 comments, and, in each case, a final decision will be generated, creating four early detection variants for the RF model, namely, RF_1 , RF_5 , RF_{10} and RF_{15} .

3.4. Early detection models

240 We also consider specific early detection models, that we adapt for the cyberbullying early detection problem. In particular, we adapt two early detection models that have reported good results [39, 40]: threshold and dual.

Taking into account that this is not a classical binary classification problem because a non-final decision can be emitted, the threshold model is based on one learning model, which is trained using the features described in Section 3.2, and it integrates a decision function based on the class probabilities to determine if enough evidence is available to proceed with a firm decision. Initially, the decision function for the threshold model is defined as:

$$\delta_1(m, th_+(), th_-())$$

245 Where m denotes a machine learning model used in (e.g. one of the baseline models), $th_+()$ is a threshold function used to set the limit for a positive final decision and $th_-()$ is the threshold function to set the limit for a negative decision. The threshold model is an adaptation of the singleton model from [40] where the threshold functions were set for batch processing (i.e. groups of posts), while in our model each post is processed individually.

We have explored different threshold functions, ranging from independent functions for positive and negative decisions to several decreasing functions depending on the number of posts processed. Contrary to [40], the best and most stable performance was obtained with a constant function of the form, $th() = k$, for both cases, positive and negative. This may be motivated because we provide a fine grain time evaluation, validating one comment at a time, opposed to the batch evaluation performed in [40]. In the experimental evaluation we analyse the performance for different values of k .

We have also tested the order in which threshold functions are applied (i.e. first th_+ () and then th_- ()), or vice versa), obtaining the same results for both cases. In our experiments, we will execute first the positive threshold and then the negative.

On the other side, the objective of the dual model is to predict independently each option (i.e. positive and negative). In this sense, and inspired by multiclass classifiers one-versus-all, the dual model consists of two independent learning models, each one trained with an independent set of features. One model is trained to detect positive cases (denoted as m_+), while the other is trained to detect negative cases (denoted as m_-). Again, we adapt the proposal from [40] by defining a decision function of the form:

$$\delta_2(m_+, m_-, th_+(), th_-())$$

Where, m_+ is the learning model responsible for positive predictions and m_- is the model in charge of negative predictions. As in the previous case, th_+ () and th_- () are the threshold functions for positive and negative cases, which, in this case, are associated with their respective models, m_+ and m_- . Following the lead of the previous model, we considered different constant functions for both thresholds.

Based on the baseline models, we have defined different threshold and dual model implementations that are expected to capture in a better way the special characteristics of the cyberbullying early detection problem.

3.5. Evaluation metrics

270 As evaluation metrics we will consider two metrics specifically designed for the early detection problem, although applied in a different environment: Early Risk Detection Error (*ERDE*) [63] and latency-weighted F1 [64]. In both cases, they were used to measure performance on the early detection of depression on individuals based on their posts on social networks.

275 The *ERDE* metric is measured at a specific point, o , and for a session s after processing k comments is defined as follows:

$$ERDE_o(s_i, k) = \begin{cases} \frac{\sum_{s_i \in S \wedge b_{s_i} = true} 1}{|S|} & \text{if False Positive} \\ 1 & \text{if False Negative} \\ 1 - \frac{1}{1+e^{k-o}} & \text{if True Positive} \\ 0 & \text{if True Negative} \end{cases}$$

In case of wrong predictions (false positive or negative) the error will increase, in the former proportionally to the number of positive cases and in the latter by 1. A true negative will not increase the error, but a true positive may impact 280 negatively if the number of posts required to make the prediction surpasses the measuring point o .

The latency-weighted F1, or in short $F_{latency}$ or *F1-latency*, is proposed by Sadeque et al. as an alternative to the ERDE metric, combining both latency and accuracy [64]. The F-latency metric is defined as:

$$F_{latency}(s_i, k) = F1 \cdot \left(1 - \underset{s_i \in S \wedge b_{s_i} = true}{median} \left(-1 + \frac{2}{1 + e^{-p(k-1)}} \right) \right)$$

285 Where, p is a parameter that determines how quickly the penalty should increase, which is set to achieve 50% of latency penalty at the median number of items and $F1$ is the standard *F-measure* that is calculated as the harmonic mean of precision and recall.

Note how *ERDE* is an error measure and, therefore, values closer to 0 are 290 better, while for $F_{latency}$ values closer to 1 are representative of good results.

Some limitations have been reported for the *ERDE* metric [65, 66] and so, we will rely more on $F_{latency}$. By default, we report results for $ERDE_{o=5}$ and p is set to 0.02288 for $F_{latency}$. Also, in the first experiments we will provide results for precision and recall, as complementary values.

295 4. Experimental evaluation

For evaluation purposes, we use 80% of the dataset for training and the remaining is used for testing. Note that the dataset has been divided by social media sessions and each session includes all its posts. The posts are presented to the models chronological and sequentially in order to make a prediction.

300 In the first set of experiments, we validate the performance of the baseline models. We start by presenting on Table 2 and 3 the results for baseline models after processing 5 comments.

Table 2 presents the performance for the individual features considered in this work for *ERDE* and $F_{latency}$ as early detection metrics, and also precision 305 and recall are presented for completeness.

The first five group of features correspond to those reported on [47] and we can observe that the best performance is obtained by comment features, both in terms of $F_{latency}$ and *ERDE*. This is motivated because comments concentrate the information that changes as the session advances, while the other features 310 are shared for the whole session. Also note how the second best performance (both for $F_{latency}$ and *ERDE*) are media session features and how the highest precision is achieved by LDA features, although performance for early detection metrics is modest.

Regarding the features proposed, we observe that BoW features achieve 315 modest results in terms of $F_{latency}$ and *ERDE*, somehow expected, since their capacity to identify similarities would be limited to textual equivalence, while time features reach reasonable results in terms of early detection.

However, it is interesting to note that BoW and time features obtain good precision scores: the latter obtains the best score and the former is second best,

Table 2: Results for baseline models after processing 5 comments using individual groups of features. Best results for each group of features are highlighted for both $ERDE$ and $F_{latency}$ and underlined for precision and recall.

	RF_5	AB_5	ET_5	SVC_5	LR_5
Profile owner features					
$ERDE$	0.1757	0.1685	0.1617	0.2054	0.1712
$F_{latency}$	0.1414	0.1363	0.2672	0.2759	0.1272
Precision	0.1905	0.3333	<u>0.4118</u>	0.1805	0.2500
Recall	0.1212	0.0909	<u>0.2121</u>	<u>0.7273</u>	0.0909
Media session features					
$ERDE$	0.1609	0.1746	0.1599	0.1967	0.1710
$F_{latency}$	0.2881	0.0465	0.2783	0.2196	0.0000
Precision	0.4000	0.1250	<u>0.4667</u>	0.1625	0.0000
Recall	0.2424	0.0303	0.2121	<u>0.3939</u>	0.0000
Comment features					
$ERDE$	0.1642	0.1694	0.1556	0.1627	0.1575
$F_{latency}$	0.2121	0.1332	0.3368	0.2776	0.3348
Precision	0.4167	0.3000	<u>0.5000</u>	0.3636	0.4167
Recall	0.1515	0.0909	<u>0.2727</u>	0.2424	<u>0.3030</u>
LDA features					
$ERDE$	0.1633	0.1738	0.1668	0.1686	0.1705
$F_{latency}$	0.1909	0.1193	0.1735	0.1660	0.2045
Precision	<u>0.5714</u>	0.2000	0.3636	0.3077	0.2609
Recall	0.1212	0.0909	0.1212	0.1212	<u>0.1818</u>
Video features					
$ERDE$	0.1728	0.1719	0.1728	0.1719	0.1719
$F_{latency}$	0.0489	0.0000	0.0489	0.0000	0.0000
Precision	<u>0.1667</u>	0.0000	<u>0.1667</u>	0.0000	0.0000
Recall	<u>0.0303</u>	0.0000	<u>0.0303</u>	0.0000	0.0000
BoW features					
$ERDE$	0.1659	0.1719	0.1685	0.1710	0.1710
$F_{latency}$	0.1468	0.0502	0.1363	0.0000	0.0000
Precision	<u>0.5000</u>	0.2000	0.3333	0.0000	0.0000
Recall	<u>0.0909</u>	0.0303	<u>0.0909</u>	0.0000	0.0000
Time features					
$ERDE$	0.1730	0.1745	0.1581	0.1740	0.1710
$F_{latency}$	0.1497	0.0000	0.2726	0.1909	0.0000
Precision	0.2222	0.0000	<u>0.6667</u>	0.2222	0.0000
Recall	0.1212	0.0000	<u>0.1818</u>	<u>0.1818</u>	0.0000

320 tied with comment features. In the case of BoW features, we consider that it is due to the fact that there are terms that are repeated on multiple cyberbullying

comments and these features will identify them, although a high number of false negatives is generated (note the low recall value) because the same terms will appear on normal comments. Regarding the time features, the high precision
325 confirms our intuition from section 3.2 suggesting that time difference between cyberbullying comments tends to be shorter but, at the same time, some normal comments will present the same characteristic, producing low recall values. In summary, the features proposed do not outperform baseline features in terms of early detection, but they are expected to be a good complement, as we will
330 discuss later.

If we focus on the models, Random Forest and Extra Trees obtain consistently the best values in terms of $F_{latency}$, with ET_5 being the best performing method just using comment features. On the other side, AdaBoost and Linear Regression are the methods with a lower performance. These results contrast
335 with [47], where AdaBoost was the best performing model, which emphasizes the differences between cyberbullying prediction and early detection.

Table 3 presents the results obtained when combining features. We start by combining all features from [47], that constitutes our baseline. The best performing model is linear SVC, improving precision and recall over individual
340 features, but not outperforming $F_{latency}$ nor $ERDE$ from individual comment features.

When incorporating, individually, BoW and time features, the performance increases for RF, AB and ET with respect to the baseline, while it decreases for SVC and LR, suggesting that models based on the data space underperform in
345 this problem. Analysing each feature individually, we observe that the bigger improvement is obtained by time features, pointing towards reiteration as an important characteristic in the early detection of cyberbullying.

When adding both features, $F_{latency}$ and $ERDE$ further improve for RF and ET with respect to individual features. However, the best $F_{latency}$ score
350 remains in AB_5 and, although being close, it does not improve the comment feature performance on Table 2, but the best precision score is achieved.

This fact just stresses the peculiarities of the cyberbullying early detection

Table 3: Results for baseline models after processing 5 comments using combinations of features. Best results for each combination are highlighted for both $ERDE$ and $F_{latency}$ and underlined for precision and recall.

	RF_5	AB_5	ET_5	SVC_5	LR_5
Profile owner, media session, comment, LDA, video features					
$ERDE$	0.1650	0.1663	0.1625	0.1665	0.1711
$F_{latency}$	0.1507	0.2849	0.2219	0.3141	0.0516
Precision	<u>0.6000</u>	0.2941	0.5000	0.2826	0.2500
Recall	<u>0.0909</u>	0.3030	0.1515	<u>0.3939</u>	0.0303
+ BoW features					
$ERDE$	0.1641	0.1663	0.1608	0.1815	0.1711
$F_{latency}$	0.1547	0.2849	0.2545	0.2386	0.0516
Precision	<u>0.7500</u>	0.2941	0.5000	0.2000	0.2500
Recall	0.0909	0.3030	0.1818	<u>0.3333</u>	0.0303
+ Time features					
$ERDE$	0.1624	0.1593	0.1599	0.1980	0.1719
$F_{latency}$	0.1957	0.3332	0.2603	0.2688	0.0502
Precision	<u>0.6667</u>	0.3667	0.5455	0.1835	0.2000
Recall	0.1212	0.3333	0.1818	<u>0.6061</u>	0.0303
+ BoW + Time features					
$ERDE$	0.1615	0.1593	0.1573	0.1908	0.1719
$F_{latency}$	0.2009	0.3332	0.2969	0.2726	0.0502
Precision	<u>0.8000</u>	0.3667	0.5833	0.1935	0.2000
Recall	0.1212	0.3333	0.2121	<u>0.5455</u>	0.0303

problem and how it differs from a standard classification problem, where only the accuracy is relevant without taking into account the time required to make the prediction (i.e. number of posts). To further study the time impact in the models performance, we analyse on Figures 2 and 3 the performance of the different models with respect to the number of posts processed.

Figure 2 presents one graph for each feature group from Tables 2 and 3 with $F_{latency}$ score for all models. For the sake of presentation we have removed video feature graph from both figures as it provided the lowest performance and did not contribute to the discussion. The graph labelled "BS" represents the combination of owner profile, media session, comments, LDA and video features from [47] that constitutes our baseline features.

Interestingly, for the owner profile and media session features the negative

Figure 2: $F_{latency}$ for all models. One graph is included for each feature and their combinations. BS graph refers to the combination of Profile, Media, Comments, LDA and Video features.

365 impact in the performance as the time progresses is clear, with the performance
for all models decreasing as more posts are processed, since these features do
not change as new comments are processed. On the other hand, comment,
LDA, BoW and time features present a more heterogeneous behaviour as time
progresses, since there is a dispute between the potential improvement of using
370 more posts versus the negative impact in performance.

Regarding the comment feature, the best performance is achieved by ET_5
model with 0.3368, closely followed by LR_5 with 0.3348 (see Table 2) and, as
more posts are read, their performance degrades. On the contrary, the Random
Forest model steadily increases its performance as more posts are processed,
375 reaching almost 0.3 with RF_{15} . This suggests that RF requires more data
from the comments to provide more precise predictions, while ET and LR can
generate good enough predictions using less posts.

For the LDA, BoW and Time features, Extra Tree achieves the best perfor-
mance in all cases, although at different points. Although for LDA, ET requires

380 processing 15 posts to achieve the best performance (0.3028), it shows again
 good results with few posts for BoW (ET_1 achieves a $F_{latency}$ score of 0.2979)
 and Time (after processing 5 posts, ET scores 0.2726).

Focusing on BS features, SVC_1 is the best performing model achieving
 0.3333 $F_{latency}$ score, but its performance decreases as more posts are read.

385 Finally, the best score is obtained combining all features (i.e. BS+BoW+Time)
 by ET_{15} with 0.3657, clearly outperforming the same model with comment fea-
 tures. Consequently, this score constitutes our baseline and the value that is
 expected to be improved by the specific early detection models.

Figure 3: $ERDE$ for all models. One graph is included for each feature and their combinations. BS graph refers to the combination of Profile, Media, Comments, LDA and Video features.

Figure 3 shows the performance for the $ERDE$ metric and it basically mimics
 390 the results from the previous figure from an error metric perspective.

It is interesting to observe how $ERDE$ values are more concentrated and
 differences are more difficult to spot but, again, Extra Tree model is performing
 consistently better than other models for most features, closely followed by
 Random Forest in many cases. Again, the best performance is achieved by
 395 ET_{15} , with a score of 0.1477.

In the remaining experiments we will focus on the best performing models, that is, Extra Tree and Random Forest, and we will report results only for $F_{latency}$ as it is able to capture more appropriately the performance for cyberbullying early detection. We have run all experiments including all models, but
400 the other models kept providing a lower performance.

The next set of experiments validates the performance of the threshold model for both, Random Forest and Extra Tree. We set $th_+(\cdot) = k$ and $th_-(\cdot) = l$ and we test different values for the k and l , ranging from 0.9 to 0.5. Regarding the features, we start with the baseline features (i.e. Profile owner, media session,
405 comment, LDA and video features), and we complete the results incorporating the features proposed (i.e. BoW and Time) both individually and combined. Figure 4 presents the results for the threshold model.

In this case, for each social media session, the number of posts required to produce a final result (i.e. positive or negative) will vary because the class
410 probability must be higher than the threshold and, therefore, the posts processed will vary for each session.

Focusing on the threshold values, we observe that, consistently, the best values are achieved when $th_+(\cdot) = 0.5$ and, as the negative threshold (i.e. $th_-(\cdot)$) increases, so does the performance up to 0.8 (decreasing at 0.9), for both models,
415 RF and ET. In fact, the top score, 0.4615, is obtained by ET with $th_+(\cdot) = 0.5$ and $th_-(\cdot) = 0.8$ including all features (BS+BoW+Time), improving the baseline performance from the previous experiment (Figure 2) by 26%.

Comparing both machine learning models, we observe that the best performing configuration of ET (i.e. $th_+(\cdot) = 0.5$) is systematically better than RF, for
420 all different feature groups and for all negative threshold values, with RF only getting close with $th_+(\cdot) = 0.5$ and $th_-(\cdot) = 0.8$.

Random Forest presents a different behaviour, with very low scores for the lower values of $th_-(\cdot)$, but improving significantly at the higher values of the negative threshold. Interestingly, the best performance for RF is also achieved
425 with $th_+(\cdot) = 0.5$ and $th_-(\cdot) = 0.8$, at 0.4484, but with features BS+Time, closely followed by BS+BoW.

Figure 4: $F_{latency}$ for threshold model using Random Forest (first row) and Extra Tree (second row). One graph is included for each value of $th_-(l) = l$. The X axis represents the values of $th_+(k) = k$. BS refers to the combination of Profile, Media, Comments, LDA and Video features.

In general, RF presents a more similar performance for the different feature groups (i.e. lines are closer in the graphs), while on ET the group including all features is consistently providing the best scores (i.e. purple line steadily on top). This may be motivated because RF requires an important confidence level to properly identify negative sessions (i.e. non-cyberbullying), while ET (using all features) is able to identify them correctly with lower class probabilities.

In the final set of experiments, we validate the performance of the dual model. For this purpose, we set initially $th_+(k) = 0.5$ and $th_-(l) = 0.8$, and present the results on Table 4 for Random Forest and Table 5 for Extra Tree. Since the dual variant requires two independent models we present a grid, where rows correspond to the features used by the negative model (best value for each row is highlighted) while columns represent the features employed by the positive model (best value for each column is underlined).

Firstly, focusing on the results for Random Forest (Table 4) we observe that

Table 4: Results for $F_{latency}$ for dual models based on Random Forest, with $th_+(\cdot) = 0.5$ and $th_-(\cdot) = 0.8$. Best value for each row (features negative model) is highlighted. Best value for each column (features positive model) is underlined. PO: Profile owner, MS: Media session, C: Comment, V: Video, BS: Profile owner + Media session + Comments + LDA + Video features, All: BS + BoW + Time.

	PO	MS	C	LDA	V	BoW	Time	BS	+BoW	+Time	All
PO	<u>0.148</u>	<u>0.302</u>	0.381	0.373	<u>0.051</u>	0.290	0.237	0.327	0.385	0.292	0.261
MS	<u>0.148</u>	<u>0.302</u>	0.378	0.343	0.049	0.282	0.271	0.407	0.448	0.421	0.400
C	<u>0.148</u>	0.302	0.182	0.286	<u>0.051</u>	0.269	0.187	0.233	0.273	0.178	0.195
LDA	<u>0.148</u>	0.302	0.233	0.264	<u>0.051</u>	0.264	0.231	0.238	0.244	0.233	0.244
V	0.141	<u>0.302</u>	0.346	0.329	0.049	0.293	0.245	0.370	0.386	0.364	0.313
BoW	<u>0.148</u>	0.302	0.267	0.271	<u>0.051</u>	0.211	0.212	0.233	0.267	0.267	0.286
Time	<u>0.148</u>	0.302	0.185	0.333	<u>0.051</u>	0.269	0.272	0.233	0.261	0.217	0.227
BS	0.143	<u>0.302</u>	0.338	0.395	0.049	0.278	0.286	0.382	0.424	0.431	0.403
+BoW	0.143	<u>0.302</u>	0.346	0.353	0.049	0.278	0.227	0.409	0.424	0.419	0.362
+Time	0.141	<u>0.302</u>	<u>0.386</u>	<u>0.443</u>	0.049	<u>0.297</u>	<u>0.304</u>	<u>0.416</u>	0.459	<u>0.448</u>	<u>0.426</u>
All	0.147	<u>0.302</u>	0.377	0.423	0.049	0.295	0.270	0.402	0.443	0.424	0.395

best results are obtained when using baseline and BoW features for the positive model. In fact, the best score, 0.459, is obtained in combination with baseline and time features for the negative model, confirming the good behaviour of our proposed features. Note that this score improves the performance for the
445 threshold model using RF, but does not overcome ET threshold model.

In general terms, when the positive model uses the baseline features in combination with our proposed features (i.e. last four columns on Table 4) the highest concentration of $F_{latency}$ values are obtained for the dual model based on Random Forest.

450 Regarding Extra Tree (Table 5), overall, it achieves a better performance than Random Forest. In fact, we corroborated that the $F_{latency}$ average value for Table 5 (i.e. 0.2964) is significantly higher than average $F_{latency}$ for Table 4 (i.e. 0.2755).

Similarly to the previous case, the last four columns condense the highest
455 score values for the whole table. This confirms the importance of considering significant features for the positive model in order to discriminate correctly cyberbullying sessions. In fact, the use of simple features for the positive models

Table 5: Results for $F_{latency}$ for dual models based on Extra Tree, with $th_+(\cdot) = 0.5$ and $th_-(\cdot) = 0.8$. Best value for each row (features negative model) is highlighted. Best value for each column (features positive model) is underlined. PO: Profile owner, MS: Media session, C: Comment, V: Video, BS: Profile owner + Media session + Comments + LDA + Video features, All: BS + BoW + Time.

	PO	MS	C	LDA	V	BoW	Time	BS	+BoW	+Time	All
PO	<u>0.364</u>	<u>0.302</u>	<u>0.392</u>	<u>0.362</u>	0.049	0.342	<u>0.336</u>	0.357	<u>0.400</u>	0.437	0.472
MS	<u>0.364</u>	<u>0.302</u>	0.379	0.360	0.049	<u>0.359</u>	<u>0.336</u>	0.437	0.372	0.442	0.434
C	<u>0.364</u>	<u>0.302</u>	0.200	0.200	<u>0.051</u>	0.257	0.187	0.302	0.241	0.345	0.436
LDA	<u>0.364</u>	<u>0.302</u>	0.211	0.219	<u>0.051</u>	0.250	0.208	0.286	0.273	0.316	0.386
V	<u>0.364</u>	<u>0.302</u>	0.374	0.293	0.049	0.358	0.282	0.333	0.327	0.404	0.404
BoW	<u>0.364</u>	<u>0.302</u>	0.310	0.222	<u>0.051</u>	0.243	0.200	0.339	0.262	0.333	0.400
Time	<u>0.364</u>	<u>0.302</u>	0.262	0.240	<u>0.051</u>	0.274	0.208	0.286	0.254	0.316	0.393
BS	<u>0.364</u>	<u>0.302</u>	0.282	0.260	<u>0.051</u>	0.279	0.227	0.339	0.316	0.343	0.348
+BoW	<u>0.364</u>	<u>0.302</u>	0.329	0.302	<u>0.051</u>	0.306	0.276	0.353	0.273	0.382	0.412
+Time	<u>0.364</u>	<u>0.302</u>	0.222	0.231	<u>0.051</u>	0.260	0.212	0.313	0.215	0.305	0.388
All	<u>0.364</u>	<u>0.302</u>	0.358	0.329	<u>0.051</u>	0.329	0.276	<u>0.448</u>	0.371	0.394	0.462

keeps the performance of the system below 0.4 in all cases.

For Extra Tree, most best scores apply all features for the positive model. However, it is interesting to observe how the use of simple features on the
460 negative model (e.g. Profile owner), leads to the best score (0.472), something that was already observed in previous works [40]. This may be motivated by the fact that multiple characteristics are required to determine if a social media session corresponds to cyberbullying, while a non-cyberbullying session can be
465 decided in a much simpler way, using less information, since it has already being discarded as cyberbullying.

Finally, we have further explored the performance of the dual model by analysing combinations of best performing positive model features (i.e. BS, BS+BoW, BS+Time, BS+BoW+Time) with all negative model features, for
470 different values of $th_+(\cdot)$ and $th_-(\cdot)$. On Figure 5 we show $F_{latency}$ scores only for Extra Tree since it provided significantly better results than Random Forest.

From the figure we observe that lower values of th_+ keep concentrating the highest scores. In fact, the best performance is obtained with $th_+(\cdot) = 0.5$ and $th_-(\cdot) = 0.6$ using all features for the positive model and profile owner features

Figure 5: $F_{latency}$ for dual model using Extra Tree. Columns represent positive model features (i.e. BS, BS+BoW, BS+Time, BS+BoW+Time), while rows represent negative model features. The X axis represents the values of $th_+(\cdot) = k$, while one line is included for each value of $th_-(\cdot) = l$. BS refers to the combination of Profile, Media, Comments, LDA and Video features.

475 for the negative model. This configuration achieves $F_{latency} = 0.5217$, improving
baseline performance from Figure 2 by 42% and best threshold model by 13%.

Interestingly, the top five configurations use all features for the positive
model and profile owner features for the negative model, with different vari-
ations of threshold configurations (note the upper right graph from Figure 5).
480 This corroborates findings from previous experiments (Table 5), and confirms
that an independent feature of the social media session, such as the owner char-
acteristics, is relevant for identification of non-cyberbullying sessions, while the
classification as cyberbullying requires specific session characteristics (e.g. com-
ment features, BoW or time).

485 Focusing on the threshold values, best performing configurations set $th_+(\cdot)$
always on the low side (i.e. values 0.5 and 0.6), while $th_-(\cdot)$ takes values from the
whole range. This, in combination with the use of all features for the positive
model, suggest the importance of defining a positive model highly capable of
properly detecting cyberbullying cases, with low class probabilities to reduce
490 detection time and, hence, requiring a low threshold. Meanwhile, the negative
model relies mainly on the use of simple features to accurately detect negative
cases, once they have been discarded as positive.

Regarding the use of BoW and Time, added to baseline features on the posi-
tive model (second and third columns on Figure 5, respectively), they provide
495 good results but below the use of all features. It is interesting to note how, for
BS+BoW the top performance is obtained when $th_+(\cdot) = 0.6$, while BS+Time
achieves its best score with $th_+(\cdot) = 0.5$ and, from there, the performance de-
grades.

5. Conclusions

500 In this paper, we introduced the cyberbullying early detection problem and
we proposed two feature groups, specifically designed for this problem: BoW
and time features. Moreover, we have also adapted two specific machine learning
models, threshold and dual, and validated their behaviour in our evaluation.

The experimental evaluation was based on a real world dataset from the
505 Vine social network and we used specific time-aware metrics (i.e. *ERDE* and
F_{latency}). Our results show how the threshold model is able to improve the
state-of-the-art detection models by 26% and the dual model is able to further
increase this improvement up to 42%, in both cases using the Extra Tree model
as basis. Moreover, the combination of proposed features along with baseline
510 features (i.e. profile owner, media session, comment, LDA and video features)
lead to the best performance for both, threshold and dual models.

In the near future, we expect to extend this research in several ways. First,
we would like to explore heterogeneous combinations of different machine learn-
ing models on the dual model. For example, Extra Tree for the positive model,
515 while Random Forest for the negative model. Second, we plan to further extend
the features regarding comments, as these concentrate most of the information
for the early detection. Third, we would like to investigate an evaluation based
on time, instead of number of posts, since it may be relevant for the early de-
tection of cyberbullying. Finally, we intend to experiment with other datasets
520 from some other social media platforms to validate our approach and generalize
the results.

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